

Versioned Archive and Review of Biotic
Interactions and Taxon Names Found within
globalbioticinteractions/cpc-pollinators
hash://md5/08af23b0f88d741237b47e8830db14dc

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2026-06-03

Abstract

Life on Earth is sustained by complex interactions between organisms and their environment. These biotic interactions can be captured in datasets and published digitally. We present a review and archiving process for such an openly accessible digital interactions dataset of known origin and discuss its outcome. The dataset under review, named globalbioticinteractions/cpc-pollinators, has fingerprint hash://md5/08af23b0f88d741237b47e8830db14dc, is 7.95MiB in size and contains 17,078 interactions with 2 unique types of associations (e.g., flowersVisitedBy) between 2,560 primary taxa (e.g., *Symphyotrichum lentum*) and 2,110 associated taxa (e.g., Bees). This report includes detailed summaries of interaction data, a taxonomic review from multiple catalogs, and an archived version of the dataset from which the reviews are derived.

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Introduction

Data Review and Archive

Data review and archiving can be a time-consuming process, especially when done manually. This review report aims to help facilitate both activities. It automates the archiving of datasets, including Darwin Core archives, and is a citable backup of a version of the dataset. Additionally, an automatic review of species interaction claims made in the dataset is generated and registered with Global Biotic Interactions (J. H. Poelen, Simons, and Mungall 2014).

This review includes summary statistics about, and observations about, the dataset under review :

National Database Plant Pollinators. Center for Plant Conservation at San Diego Zoo Global. Accessed via <https://saveplants.org/national-collection/pollinator-search/> on 2020-06-05. <https://github.com/globalbioticinteractions/cpc-pollinators/archive/a64674001b3fce1c5a4896d8c29b4bcb024e6f0b.zip> 2026-06-02T14:38:45.770Z hash://md5/08af23b0f88d741237b47e8830db14dc

Methods

The review is performed through programmatic scripts that leverage tools like Preston (Elliott et al. 2025), Elton (Kuhn, Poelen, and Leinweber 2025), Nomer (Salim and Poelen 2025), globinizer (J. Poelen, Seltmann, and Mietchen 2024) combined with third-party tools like grep, mlr, tail and head.

Table 1: Tools used in this review process

tool name	version
preston	0.11.1
elton	0.16.11
nomer	0.6.5
globinizer	0.4.0
mlr	6.0.0
jq	1.6
yq	4.25.3
pandoc	3.1.6.1
duckdb	1.3.1
mapserver	7.6.4

The review process can be described in the form of the script below ¹.

```
# get versioned copy of the dataset (size approx. 7.95MiB) under review
elton pull globalbioticinteractions/cpc-pollinators

# generate review notes
elton review globalbioticinteractions/cpc-pollinators \
> review.tsv

# export indexed interaction records
elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/cpc-pollinators \
> interactions.tsv

# export names and align them with the Catalogue of Life using Nomer
elton names globalbioticinteractions/cpc-pollinators \
| nomer append col \
> name-alignment.tsv
```

or visually, in a process diagram.

You can find a copy of the full review script at [check-data.sh](https://github.com/ncbi/check-data.sh). See also GitHub and Codeberg.

¹Note that you have to first get the data (e.g., via `elton pull globalbioticinteractions/cpc-pollinators`) before being able to generate reviews (e.g., `elton review globalbioticinteractions/cpc-pollinators`), extract interaction claims (e.g., `elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/cpc-pollinators`), or list taxonomic names (e.g., `elton names globalbioticinteractions/cpc-pollinators`)

Figure 1: Review Process Overview

Results

In the following sections, the results of the review are summarized ². Then, links to the detailed review reports are provided.

Files

An extensive list of files produced as part of the review process can be found in Appendix A. Review Files.

Archived Dataset

Note that *data.zip* file in this archive contains the complete, unmodified archived dataset under review.

Biotic Interactions

Figure 2: Biotic Interaction Data Model

In this review, biotic interactions (or biotic associations) are modeled as a primary (aka subject, source) organism interacting with an associate (aka object, target) organism. The dataset under review classified the primary/associate organisms with specific taxa. The primary and associate organisms The kind of interaction is documented as an interaction type.

The dataset under review, named `globalbioticinteractions/cpc-pollinators`, has fingerprint hash: `//md5/08af23b0f88d741237b47e8830db14dc`, is 7.95MiB in size

²Disclaimer: The results in this review should be considered friendly, yet naive, notes from an unsophisticated robot. Please keep that in mind when considering the review results.

and contains 17,078 interactions with 2 unique types of associations (e.g., flowersVisitedBy) between 2,560 primary taxa (e.g., *Symphytotrichum lentum*) and 2,110 associated taxa (e.g., Bees).

An exhaustive list of indexed interaction claims can be found in gzipped csv, tsv, geopackage and parquet archives. To facilitate discovery, a preview of claims available in the gzipped html page at indexed-interactions.html.gz are shown below.

The exhaustive list was used to create the following data summaries below.

Table 2: Sample of Indexed Interaction Claims

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeNam	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Jacquemontia reclinata	flowersVisitedBy	Acanthoscelides	Pinto-Torres, E. & Koptur, S. (2009). Hanging by a coastal strand: breeding system of a federally endangered morning-glory of the south-eastern Florida coast, <i>Jacquemontia reclinata</i> . <i>Annals of Botany</i> , 104, 1301-1311
Hesperidanthus suffrutescens	flowersVisitedBy	Andrena	Lewis, M. (2013). Roads and the Reproductive Ecology of <i>Hesperidanthus suffrutescens</i> . Dissertation. Utah State University, Logan, Utah

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Sclerocactus wetlandicus	flowersVisitedBy	Andrena	Tepedino, V.J., Griswold, T.L. & Bowlin, W.R. (2010). Reproductive Biology, Hybridization, and Flower Visitors of Rare Sclerocactus Taxa in Utah's Uintah Basin. Western North American Naturalist, 70, 377-386
Hesperidanthus suffrutescens	flowersVisitedBy	Andrena merriami	Lewis, M.B. & Schupp, E.W. (2014). Reproductive Ecology of the Endangered Utah Endemic Hesperidanthus suffrutescens with Implications for Conservation. The American Midland Naturalist, 172, 236-251

Table 3: Most Frequently Mentioned Interaction Types (up to 20 most frequent)

interactionTypeName	count
flowersVisitedBy	11986
pollinatedBy	5092

Table 4: Most Frequently Mentioned Primary Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	count
<i>Symphytotrichum lentum</i>	341
<i>Asclepias eastwoodiana</i>	260
<i>Rudbeckia scabrifolia</i>	192
<i>Eryngium pendletonensis</i>	176
<i>Erigeron ovinus</i>	114
<i>Erigeron arisolius</i>	114
<i>Geranium caespitosum</i>	103
<i>Cirsium arvense</i>	103
<i>Achillea millefolium</i>	97
<i>Monarda fistulosa</i>	92
<i>Medicago sativa</i>	84
<i>Heterotheca villosa</i>	84
<i>Apocynum androsaemifolium</i>	81
<i>Eriogonum umbellatum</i>	78
<i>Baccharis plummerae</i> ssp. <i>glabrata</i>	77
<i>Cirsium crassicaule</i>	73
<i>Taraxacum officinale</i>	72
<i>Carduus nutans</i>	71
<i>Rubus deliciosus</i>	70

Table 5: Most Frequently Mentioned Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

targetTaxonName	count
Bees	1203
Lepidoptera	787
Diptera	480
Bombus	276
Coleoptera	266
Trochilidae	265
Insecta	189
<i>Apis mellifera</i>	188
Hymenoptera	182
<i>Vanessa cardui</i>	174
<i>Apis</i>	159
<i>Pieris rapae</i>	125
Self pollinated	121
Wasps	120
Syrphidae	112

targetTaxonName	count
Strymon melinus	107
Colias philodice	101
Colias eurytheme	99
Halictidae	97

Table 6: Most Frequent Interactions between Primary and Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	count
Aconitum	pollinatedBy	Bombus	7
Achillea millefolium	pollinatedBy	Bees	7
Brodiaea insignis	flowersVisitedBy	Eucera	6
Phlox longifolia	pollinatedBy	Lepidoptera	6
Astragalus drummondii	pollinatedBy	Lepidoptera	6
Campsis radicans	pollinatedBy	Trochilidae	6
Chamaebatiaria millefolium	pollinatedBy	Lepidoptera	6
Lobelia cardinalis	pollinatedBy	Trochilidae	6
Oenothera pallida	pollinatedBy	Lepidoptera	6
Peritoma serrulata	pollinatedBy	Lepidoptera	6
Prunus virginiana	pollinatedBy	Bees	6
Rudbeckia laciniata	pollinatedBy	Lepidoptera	5
Rudbeckia hirta	pollinatedBy	Bees	5
Acacia	pollinatedBy	Bees	5
Agave	pollinatedBy	Chiroptera	5
Aquilegia canadensis	pollinatedBy	Bees	5
Aquilegia formosa	pollinatedBy	Trochilidae	5
Arctostaphylos edmundsii	pollinatedBy	Bees	5
Erigeron	pollinatedBy	Lepidoptera	5

Interaction Networks

The figures below provide a graph view on the dataset under review. The first shows a summary network on the kingdom level, and the second shows how interactions on the family level. It is important to note that both network graphs were first aligned taxonomically using the Catalogue of Life. Please refer to the original (or verbatim) taxonomic names for a more original view on the interaction data.

You can download the indexed dataset under review at indexed-interactions.csv.gz. A tab-separated file can be found at indexed-interactions.tsv.gz

Figure 3: Interactions on taxonomic kingdom rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life download svg

Figure 4: Interactions on the taxonomic family rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life. [download svg](#)

Geospatial Distribution

If geospatial information was extracted from the dataset under review, the map below will show their distribution. These maps were generated using MapServer (McKenna et al. 2025) tools configured via map configuration indexed-interactions.map :

```
MAP
  SIZE 1600 800
  EXTENT -180 -90 180 90
  PROJECTION
    "init=epsg:4326"
  END
  LAYER # MODIS WMS map from NASA
    NAME "modis_nasa"
    TYPE RASTER
    OFFSITE 0 0 0
    STATUS ON
    CONNECTIONTYPE WMS
    CONNECTION "https://gibs.earthdata.nasa.gov/wms/epsg4326/best/wms.cgi?"

  METADATA
    "wms_srs" "EPSG:4326"
    "wms_name" "OSM_Land_Water_Map"
    "wms_server_version" "1.1.1"
    "wms_format" "image/jpeg"
  END
  CLASS
    STYLE
      COLOR 232 232 232
      OUTLINECOLOR 32 32 32
    END
  END
  LAYER
    NAME "indexed-interactions"
    TYPE POLYGON
    STATUS ON
    CONNECTIONTYPE OGR
    CONNECTION "indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg"
    DATA "indexed-interactions-h3"
    CLASS
      STYLE
        COLORRANGE 253.0 231.0 37.0 32.0 164.0 134.0
        DATARANGE NULL NULL
        RANGEITEM "log_number_of_records"
```

```

        OUTLINECOLOR 0 0 0
      END
    END
  END
END

```

Hexagonal grid cells indicate that interactions claims are available for selected geospatial area: light yellow means relatively fewer claims, dark green relatively more claims.

Figure 5: Hexagonal grid cells indicate that interactions claims are available for selected geospatial area: light yellow means relatively fewer claims, dark green relatively more claims.

Associated data can be found in the geopackage files at indexed-interactions.gpkg for point data and indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg for data clustered in geospatial h3 hexagonals.

Learn more about the structure of this download at GloBI website, by opening a GitHub issue, or by sending an email.

Another way to discover the dataset under review is by searching for it on the GloBI website.

Taxonomic Alignment

As part of the review, all names are aligned against various name catalogs (e.g., col, ncbi, discoverlife, gbif, itis, wfo, mdd, tpt, pbdb, and worms). These alignments can help review name usage or aid in selecting of a suitable taxonomic name resource.

Table 7: Sample of Name Alignments

providedName	relationName	resolvedCatalogName	resolvedName
Abaeis nicippe	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	col	Abaeis nicippe
Abies fraseri	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	col	Abies fraseri
Abies fraseri	SYNONYM_OF	col	Abies fraseri
Abronia ammophila	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	col	Abronia ammophila

Table 8: Distribution of Taxonomic Ranks of Aligned Names by Catalog. Names that were not aligned with a catalog are counted as NAs. So, the total number of unaligned names for a catalog will be listed in their NA row.

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
col	NA	365
col	class	4
col	family	77
col	genus	498
col	kingdom	1
col	order	11
col	species	3591
col	subfamily	5
col	subgenus	9
col	subspecies	164
col	tribe	10
col	variety	20
discoverlife	NA	4028
discoverlife	species	639
gbif	NA	260
gbif	class	5
gbif	family	79
gbif	form	1
gbif	genus	509
gbif	kingdom	1
gbif	order	10
gbif	species	3602
gbif	subspecies	184
gbif	variety	121
itis	NA	505
itis	class	4
itis	family	75
itis	genus	476
itis	kingdom	1
itis	order	11
itis	species	3436
itis	subfamily	3
itis	suborder	1
itis	subspecies	149
itis	superorder	1
itis	variety	7
mdd	NA	4666
ncbi	NA	1099
ncbi	class	4

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
ncbi	cohort	1
ncbi	family	74
ncbi	genus	479
ncbi	kingdom	1
ncbi	order	11
ncbi	species	2941
ncbi	subfamily	4
ncbi	subgenus	19
ncbi	suborder	1
ncbi	subspecies	47
ncbi	varietas	2
pbdb	NA	4290
pbdb	class	4
pbdb	family	75
pbdb	genus	221
pbdb	infraclass	1
pbdb	kingdom	1
pbdb	order	10
pbdb	species	59
pbdb	subfamily	1
pbdb	suborder	3
pbdb	unranked clade	3
tpt	NA	4626
tpt	family	5
tpt	genus	2
tpt	order	2
tpt	species	31
wfo	NA	2321
wfo	genus	261
wfo	species	2067
wfo	subspecies	24
wfo	variety	17
worms	NA	3880
worms	class	3
worms	family	58
worms	genus	199
worms	kingdom	1
worms	order	11
worms	species	511
worms	subclass	1
worms	suborder	1
worms	subspecies	4
worms	variety	1

Table 9: Name relationship types per catalog. Name relationship type “NONE” means that a name was not recognized by the associated catalog. “SAME_AS” indicates either a “HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME” or “SYNONYM_OF” name relationship type. We recognize that “SYNONYM_OF” encompasses many types of nomenclatural synonymies (ICZN 1999) (e.g., junior synonym, senior synonyms).

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
col	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	3977
col	SYNONYM_OF	1209
col	NONE	365
discoverlife	NONE	4030
discoverlife	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	562
discoverlife	SYNONYM_OF	255
discoverlife	HOMONYM_OF	32
gbif	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	4623
gbif	NONE	260
gbif	SYNONYM_OF	1639
itis	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	4049
itis	NONE	505
itis	SYNONYM_OF	215
mdd	NONE	4663
mdd	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	6
ncbi	SYNONYM_OF	194
ncbi	SAME_AS	3416
ncbi	NONE	1099
pbdb	NONE	4292
pbdb	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	378
pbdb	SYNONYM_OF	25
tpt	NONE	4629
tpt	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	38
tpt	SYNONYM_OF	2
wfo	NONE	2322
wfo	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	2227
wfo	SYNONYM_OF	327
wfo	HAS_UNCHECKED_NAME	230
worms	NONE	3882
worms	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	846
worms	SYNONYM_OF	96

Table 10: List of Available Name Alignment Reports

catalog name	alignment results
col	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
ncbi	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
discoverlife	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
gbif	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
itis	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
wfo	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
mdd	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
tpt	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
pbdb	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
worms	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)

Additional Reviews

Elton, Nomer, and other tools may have difficulties interpreting existing species interaction datasets. Or, they may misbehave, or otherwise show unexpected behavior. As part of the review process, detailed review notes are kept that document possibly misbehaving, or confused, review bots. An sample of review notes associated with this review can be found below.

Table 11: First few lines in the review notes.

reviewDate	reviewCommentType	reviewComment
2026-06-03T08:34:43Z	note	missing interaction type
2026-06-03T08:34:43Z	note	missing interaction type
2026-06-03T08:34:43Z	note	missing interaction type
2026-06-03T08:34:43Z	note	found unsupported interaction type with name: [Nectar Robber and Pollen Robber]

In addition, you can find the most frequently occurring notes in the table below.

Table 12: Most frequently occurring review notes, if any.

reviewComment	count
missing interaction type	831
target taxon name missing	249
found unsupported interaction type	2
with name: [Nectar Robber and Pollen Robber]	
found unsupported interaction type	2
with name: [Nectar Robber and Pollinator]	

For additional information on review notes, please have a look at the first 500 Review Notes in html format or the download full gzipped csv or tsv archives.

GloBI Review Badge

As part of the review, a review badge is generated. This review badge can be included in webpages to indicate the review status of the dataset under review.

Figure 6: Picture of a GloBI Review Badge ³

Note that if the badge is green, no review notes were generated. If the badge is yellow, the review bots may need some help with interpreting the species interaction data.

GloBI Index Badge

If the dataset under review has been registered with GloBI, and has been successfully indexed by GloBI, the GloBI Index Status Badge will turn green. This means that the dataset under review was indexed by GloBI and is available through GloBI services and derived data products.

Figure 7: Picture of a GloBI Index Badge ⁴

If you'd like to keep track of reviews or index status of the dataset under review, please visit GloBI's dataset index ⁵ for badge examples.

³Up-to-date status of the GloBI Review Badge can be retrieved from the GloBI Review Depot

⁴Up-to-date status of the GloBI Index Badge can be retrieved from GloBI's API

⁵At time of writing (2026-06-03) the version of the GloBI dataset index was available at

Discussion

This review and archive provides a means of creating citable versions of datasets that change frequently. This may be useful for dataset managers, including natural history collection data managers, as a backup archive of a shared Darwin Core archive. It also serves as a means of creating a trackable citation for the dataset in an automated way, while also including some information about the contents of the dataset.

This review aims to provide a perspective on the dataset to aid in understanding of species interaction claims discovered. However, it is important to note that this review does *not* assess the quality of the dataset. Instead, it serves as an indication of the open-ness⁶ and FAIRness (Wilkinson et al. 2016; Trekels et al. 2023) of the dataset: to perform this review, the data was likely openly available, **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable and **R**eusable. The current Open-FAIR assessment is qualitative, and a more quantitative approach can be implemented with specified measurement units.

This report also showcases the reuse of machine-actionable (meta)data, something highly recommended by the FAIR Data Principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016). Making (meta)data machine-actionable enables more precise processing by computers, enabling even naive review bots like Nomer and Elton to interpret the data effectively. This capability is crucial for not just automating the generation of reports, but also for facilitating seamless data exchanges, promoting interoperability.

Acknowledgements

We thank the many humans that created us and those who created and maintained the data, software and other intellectual resources that were used for producing this review. In addition, we are grateful for the natural resources providing the basis for these human and bot activities. Also, thanks to <https://github.com/zygoballus> for helping improve the layout of the review tables.

Author contributions

Nomer was responsible for name alignments. Elton carried out dataset extraction, and generated the review notes. Preston tracked, versioned, and packaged, the dataset under review.

<https://globalbioticinteractions.org/datasets>

⁶According to <http://opendefinition.org/>: “Open data is data that can be freely used, reused and redistributed by anyone - subject only, at most, to the requirement to attribute and sharealike.”

Appendix A. Review Files

The following files are produced in this review:

filename	description
biblio.bib	list of bibliographic reference of this review
check-dataset.sh	data review workflow/process as expressed in a bash script
data.zip	a versioned archive of the data under review
HEAD	the digital signature of the data under review
index.docx	review in MS Word format
index.html	review in HTML format
index.md	review in Pandoc markdown format
index.pdf	review in PDF format
indexed-citations.csv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped comma-separated values file format
indexed-citations.html.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interactions claims in gzipped html file format
indexed-citations.tsv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions-col-family-col-family.svg	network diagram showing the taxon family to taxon family interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions-col-kingdom-col-kingdom.svg	network diagram showing the taxon kingdom to taxon kingdom interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions.csv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-interactions.html.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-interactions.tsv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions.parquet	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-interactions.png	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review plotted on a map
indexed-interactions.map	mapserver configuration to plot species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review on a map
indexed-interactions.gpkg	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg	geospatially clustered h3 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-sample.csv	list of species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions-sample.html	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in html format
indexed-interactions-sample.tsv	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
indexed-names.csv.gz	taxonomic names indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-names.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-col.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-col.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-itis.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-worms.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-sample.csv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
indexed-names-sample.html	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in html format
indexed-names-sample.tsv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
interaction.svg	diagram summarizing the data model used to index species interaction claims
nanopub-sample.trig	first 500 species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)

filename	description
nanopub.trig.gz	species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
process.svg	diagram summarizing the data review processing workflow
prov.nq	origin of the dataset under review as expressed in rdf/nquads
review.csv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
review.html.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped html format
review.tsv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
review-sample.csv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
review-sample.html	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in html format
review-sample.tsv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
review.svg	a review badge generated as part of the dataset review process
zenodo.json	metadata of this review expressed in Zenodo record metadata

References

- Elliott, Michael, Jorrit Poelen, Icaro Alzuru, Emilio Berti, and partha04patel. 2025. “Bio-Guoda/Preston: 0.10.5.” Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14662206>.
- ICZN. 1999. “International Code of Zoological Nomenclature.” The International Trust for Zoological Nomenclature, London, UK. <https://www.iczn.org/the-code/the-code-online/>.
- Kuhn, Tobias, and Michel Dumontier. 2014. “Trusty URIs: Verifiable, Immutable, and Permanent Digital Artifacts for Linked Data.” In *The Semantic Web: Trends and Challenges*, edited by Valentina Presutti, Claudia d’Amato, Fabien Gandon, Mathieu d’Aquin, Steffen Staab, and Anna Tordai, 395–410. Cham: Springer International Publishing.

- Kuhn, Tobias, Jorrit Poelen, and Katrin Leinweber. 2025. “Globalbioticinteractions/Elton: 0.15.1.” Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14927734>.
- McKenna, Jeff, Steve Lime, Thomas Bonfort, Jérôme Boué, Howard Butler, Seth Girvin, Tom Kralidis, et al. 2025. “MapServer.” Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17807263>.
- Poelen, Jorrit H. (ed.). 2024. “Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources Hash://Sha256/ B60c0d25a16ae77b24305782017b1a270b79b5d1746f832650 F2027ba536e276 Hash://Md5/17f1363a277ee0e4ecaf1b91c665e47e.” Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12695629>.
- Poelen, Jorrit H., James D. Simons, and Chris J. Mungall. 2014. “Global Biotic Interactions: An Open Infrastructure to Share and Analyze Species-Interaction Datasets.” *Ecological Informatics* 24 (November): 148–59. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoinf.2014.08.005>.
- Poelen, Jorrit, Katja Seltmann, and Daniel Mietchen. 2024. “Globalbioticinteractions/Globinizer: 0.4.0.” Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10647565>.
- Salim, José Augusto, and Jorrit Poelen. 2025. “Globalbioticinteractions/Nomer: 0.5.15.” Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14893840>.
- Trekels, Maarten, Debora Pignatari Drucker, José Augusto Salim, Jeff Ollerton, Jorrit Poelen, Filipi Miranda Soares, Max Rünzel, Muo Kasina, Quentin Groom, and Mariano Devoto. 2023. “WorldFAIR Project (D10.1) Agriculture-related pollinator data standards use cases report.” Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8176978>.
- Wilkinson, Mark D., Michel Dumontier, IJsbrand Jan Aalbersberg, Gabrielle Appleton, Myles Axton, Arie Baak, Niklas Blomberg, et al. 2016. “The FAIR Guiding Principles for Scientific Data Management and Stewardship.” *Scientific Data* 3 (1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>.